

DEVELOPMENT OF THE USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE CONSTRUCTION SECTOR

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Abstract. *The article describes the growing demand for artificial intelligence in the development of the world’s economies and the increasing volume of investments in this field. It also outlines the strategy for the development of artificial intelligence technologies in our country for the period up to 2030, particularly the priority directions of applying artificial intelligence technologies in the construction industry. In addition, the article highlights issues related to training specialists in this field at the Tashkent Architecture and Construction University, the effective use of artificial intelligence in mitigating seismic risks and threats, as well as in analyzing digitalized data.*

Keywords: *artificial intelligence, artificial intelligence technologies, artificial intelligence cluster, robotics, transformation, aerospace and cloud technologies, seismic safety, sustainable construction, smart city system.*

Introduction

“At present time, humanity is boldly stepping into a new stage of civilization – the era of artificial intelligence. Such technologies are deeply penetrating fields ranging from the economy to education, medicine, agriculture, and governance. In any sphere, whoever researches diligently and achieves concrete results will be ahead; the finish line belongs to them.”— President Sh. Mirziyoyev. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a technology that uses computer systems to simulate human cognitive activity and behavior. AI is widely applied in various fields, including medicine, science, engineering, education, and business [1].

One of the main directions of AI development in the economy is improving the efficiency of production processes. Using AI allows for the automation of numerous production processes, reduction of production time, minimization of errors, and enhancement of product quality. Additionally, companies can use AI to manage inventory, optimize production, improve quality control, and reduce production costs. Another important direction of AI development is the creation of new products and services. AI enables companies to develop innovative products and services that previously did not exist. Currently, worldwide investment in AI is growing rapidly. Simultaneously, many countries are developing national strategies and programs for AI advancement. According to the International Data Corporation, in 2021, global spending on AI solutions amounted to USD 383.3 billion, and by 2025, the AI market is expected to reach USD 1 trillion [2].

Main Part

It should be noted that the “Digital Uzbekistan – 2030” strategy [3] prioritizes exploring the possibilities of using virtual and augmented reality, AI, cryptography, machine learning, big data analytics, and cloud computing technologies across the country’s economic sectors. It also emphasizes the gradual automation of workplaces, robotization of production processes,

implementation of AI technologies, establishment of laboratories in higher education institutions for “Internet of Things,” robotics, and AI, as well as attracting foreign enterprises to this field.

The development of AI technologies is creating new jobs. For example, at the beginning of 2024, the number of AI-related jobs worldwide is expected to increase by 10%. Each year, the number of startups using AI technologies is growing. At the start of 2024, AI-related startups accounted for 25% of the global startup market. The penetration of AI into the construction sector is technologically lower compared to more advanced sectors, such as finance. However, growth is evident: according to some forecasts, by 2031, the global AI market in the construction sector will grow at an annual rate of 34%, expanding from USD 500 million to USD 8.6 billion.

Leading countries in AI development include the United States, China, the European Union, Japan, and South Korea. These countries have strong scientific and technological bases, large markets, consumer demand, and active support from both the government and business sectors. The United States is considered the world leader in AI innovations, hosting major technology companies such as Google, Microsoft, Amazon, Facebook, and IBM, which develop and implement advanced AI solutions across various industries [4].

At the same time, the “Strategy for the Development of Artificial Intelligence Technologies until 2030,” approved by the President’s Decree PD-358 dated October 14, 2024 [5], sets forth the following priority tasks: increasing the volume of AI-based software products and services to USD 1.5 billion by 2030; raising the share of AI-based services on the unified interactive state services portal to 10%; expanding the number of scientific laboratories working in the AI field to 10 and launching high-performance computing servers; and positioning the country among the top 50 nations in the Government AI Readiness Index. On October 21, 2025 during a visit to the IT Park in Tashkent, President Sh. Mirziyoyev emphasized that, in order to remain competitive in the current global environment of growing AI demand, three key areas require focused attention: infrastructure, open data, and workforce development.

Additionally, as part of the second phase of the IT Park project, a 12-megawatt data center will be launched in cooperation with Saudi Arabia’s Data Volt company with an investment of USD 150 million. In the next phase, capacities will be expanded to 500 megawatts with an additional investment of USD 3 billion. In Urgench, an AI-based “Smart City System” will be implemented along with the establishment of a situational center. Electricity, gas, water, heating supply, management and service companies, transport, roads, landscaping, and waste management enterprises will be integrated into a single system. AI will analyze incoming requests from each sector to provide rapid and comprehensive solutions, which is expected to save 16 billion UZS annually. All district and regional governors in the provinces, as well as heads of other ministries and agencies, were instructed to study the new Urgench experience and implement AI integration in their respective areas by the end of the year [4].

The President also highlighted that none of the universities currently producing 2,000 specialists per year have AI laboratories. By the next academic year, ten higher education institutions are planned to be equipped with modern AI laboratories. At the “New Uzbekistan” University, an “AI Cluster” operating on the “network – university – partner” principle will be launched. From the next academic year, joint educational programs in AI will be implemented in cooperation with universities ranked in the “TOP-300.” Additionally, the quotas for state grants in universities for fields such as AI, fintech, cybersecurity, IT engineering, aerospace, and cloud technologies will be increased by 35% [4].

Taking the above into account, AI also plays a crucial role in transforming the construction sector. Its application significantly improves design, construction management, building safety, and operational efficiency. Effective use of AI in construction requires close collaboration between AI specialists and construction engineers to maximize the technology's potential and bring substantial benefits to the industry.

Moreover, as highlighted in the President's Decree PD-184, dated October 20, 2025, "On Additional Measures to Ensure Seismic Safety and Improve the Effectiveness of Seismology Work" [6], AI technologies are essential for ensuring seismic safety. This includes using AI for medium- and long-term prediction of strong earthquakes (illustrated by the example of Tashkent), and analyzing the technical condition of buildings and structures for seismic resistance. Relevant measures are also outlined in PQ-309, "On Organizing the Activity of the National Research Institute of Seismic Safety and Sustainable Construction under Tashkent Architecture and Construction University" [7], and PQ-161 dated April 17, 2024, "On Measures to Improve Seismic Resistance of Buildings and Structures and Monitor Seismic Risk" [8].

In accordance with these directives, Tashkent Architecture and Construction University has launched training programs in "Artificial Intelligence" and "Computer Engineering" to prepare specialists for seismic risk mitigation, data analysis, and AI applications, incorporating international experience from Japan, China, the USA, Germany, and Turkey.

AI is transforming construction by optimizing processes from design to operation. It is applied for automation, quality control, risk management, safety on construction sites, and efficient management of resources and finances.

The key priority areas for AI use in construction are:

- **Design and Planning:** AI analyzes large datasets to create precise and optimal designs, proposes the best design options, and detects errors at early stages.
- **Construction Management:** Automating and optimizing routine tasks, as well as managing project resources and finances more accurately.
- **Construction Site Safety:** Monitoring safety with smart cameras and sensors, training workers through virtual reality simulations, and helping identify and mitigate risks.
- **Quality Control:** Analyzing data and images to automatically monitor work quality.
- **Resource Management:** Efficient management of materials and equipment.
- **Building Operations:** Assisting in building management and maintenance after construction completion.
- **Automation and Robotics:** Using robots for physically demanding or repetitive tasks, such as bricklaying.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be noted that in the near future, AI will become an integral part of our lives, much like the internet or other technologies. AI has the potential to enhance global economic efficiency, but it may also widen the digital divide between countries. AI could transform occupations that currently meet labor market demands into other professions requiring social and cognitive skills, which, in turn, may initially increase unemployment.

In the construction sector, the development of AI opens up new opportunities to improve the efficiency and quality of construction work. When integrated with other advanced technologies, AI allows for maximum automation and optimization of all processes, enabling the creation of "smart construction sites." Moreover, construction specialists who effectively use AI

technologies can significantly improve project outcomes, reduce risks, and maintain competitiveness in a digitized economy.

In other words, if AI technologies are not effectively developed and implemented, inequalities between national economies, individual companies, and workers in the labor market will continue to grow, potentially leading to social conflicts. To prevent this, governments, in cooperation with businesses, should support workers in transitioning to new, high-demand jobs, while individuals must continuously upgrade their skills to meet the needs of the modern labor market.

REFERENCES

1. Chigirova, A.S., Rafikov, R.I. Development of the use of Artificial Intelligence in the economy // International Journal of Humanities and Natural Sciences, vol. 4-4 (79), 2023, P. 220.
2. Dadashev, Z.F., Ustinova, N.G. The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on the Economy // Economic Sciences, No. 18, June, 2019, P. 57.
3. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 05.10.2020, "On approval of the Strategy 'Digital Uzbekistan - 2030' and Measures for its effective implementation," PD-6079. <https://lex.uz/docs/-5030957>
4. Today President Sh. Mirziyoev Visits the IT-Park in Tashkent. https://t.me/Press_Secretary_Uz/6370?start=em9tneg
5. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 14.10.2024, "On Approval of the Strategy for the Development of Artificial Intelligence Technologies until 2030," PD-358. <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/-7158604>
6. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 20.10.2025, "On additional measures to ensure seismic safety and further improve efficiency in the Field of Seismology," PD-184. <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/-7777660>
7. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 20.10.2025, "On measures to organize the activities of the National Institute for Seismic Safety and Sustainable Construction under the Tashkent Architecture and Construction University," PD-309. <https://www.lex.uz/docs/-7777579>
8. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 17.04.2024, "On measures to increase the earthquake resistance of buildings and structures and to improve seismic risk monitoring," PD-161. <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/6887055>